

NEW SYNTHESSES OF *trans-syn-cis* -AND *trans-anti-trans*-9-KETO-PERHYDROPHENANTHRENES

BY RAMESH CHANDRA CHATTERJEE AND BIDYUT KAMAL BHATTACHARYYA

The Mannich-Robinson reaction with 1-diethylaminobutanone-3 was applied on the β -keto-diester (III: R=H; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me), prepared from (II: R=R₁=CO₂Et; R₂=H; R₃=CN) by cyanoethylation, hydrolysis, esterification and the Dieckmann cyclisation, to yield 2- γ -ketobutyl-2:4-dicarbomethoxy-*trans*-1-decalone, which on cyclisation, followed by esterification, furnished (IV: R=CO₂Me). The latter compound on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride, followed by dehydrogenation, yielded the 9-methylphenanthrene. The compound (IV: R=CO₂Me) was hydrogenated to the saturated keto-esters which on Huang-Minlon's reduction yielded two different acids, the esters of which were separately subjected to the Barbier-Wieland degradation to produce (VIII) and (IX) respectively.

Although it has been observed that in steroid the hydrogenation of $\Delta^9:11$ double bond by Adams' catalyst in glacial acetic acid proceeds in a stereospecific manner to give the natural steroid configuration, *i.e.*, *trans-anti-trans* (Woodward *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 74, 4224; Kendall *et al.*, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, 175, 249; Shoppee and Reichstein, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1941, 24, 351; Shoppee, *ibid.*, 1940, 23, 740), yet in the present investigation the hydrogenation of 9-carbomethoxy-1:2:3:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene-3-one with palladium on charcoal was found to yield a mixture of *trans-syn-cis* and *trans-anti-trans* ring fusions of which the former was the major product.

Ethyl 2-carbomethoxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (I), prepared according to the method of Grew and Mondon (*Naturwiss.*, 1946, 11, 333; *Ber.*, 1948, 81, 279), was hydrogenated to furnish ethyl 2-carbomethoxycyclohexyl-1-cyanoacetate (II: R=R₁=CO₂Et; R₂=H; R₃=CN) which was cyanoethylated by following the procedure of Bruson ("Organic Reactions", Vol. V, p. 79) to furnish γ -cyano- γ -carbomethoxy- γ -(2-carbomethoxycyclohexyl)-butyronitrile (II: R=R₁=CO₂Et; R₂=CH₂CH₂CN; R₃=CN). The latter compound on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid yielded a crystalline tricarboxylic acid (II: R=R₁=CO₂H; R₂=CH₂CH₂CO₂H; R₃=H). The trimethyl ester (II: R=R₁=CO₂Me; R₂=CH₂CH₂CO₂Me; R₃=H) smoothly underwent the Dieckmann cyclisation with sodium dust to afford dimethyl *trans*-1-decalone-2:4-dicarboxylate (III: R=H; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me) which on hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid yielded *trans*-1-decalone-4-carboxylic acid (III: R=R₁=H; R₂=CO₂H) which was previously prepared by Novello *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1330) as well as by Downes *et al.* (*ibid.*, 1950, 72, 3464) by different routes. The β -keto-diester (III: R=H; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me) was methylated with sodium dust and methyl iodide and the methylated product (III: R=Me; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me), thus obtained, was hydrolysed with hydrochloric acid to yield crystalline 2-methyl-*trans*-1-decalone-4-carboxylic acid (III: R=Me; R₁=H; R₂=CO₂H).

The Mannich-Robinson reaction (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 53 and subsequent papers) with α -diethylaminobutanone-3 was applied on the dimethyl *trans*-1-decalone-2:4-dicarboxylate to give the open-chain compound, 2- γ -ketobutyl-2:4-dicarbomethoxy-*trans*-1-decalone (III: R = CH₂CH₂COMe; R₁ = R₂ = CO₂Me). The latter was then cyclised and decarboxylated with a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric and glacial acetic acids according to the method of Wilds and Shunk (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 65, 469) to furnish a gummy acidic material (IV: R = CO₂H), which was esterified by diazomethane to yield 9-carbomethoxy-1:2:3:4b:5:6:7:8a:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene-3-one (IV: R = CO₂Me). In order to ascertain the tricyclic skeleton of the cyclised condensation product (IV: R = CO₂Me), the latter was treated with lithium aluminium hydride in ethereal solution to furnish a diol, which on dehydrogenation with selenium yielded the known 9-methylphenanthrene (V) (Windaus *et al.*, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 1871, 1875; Haworth and Mavin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2720; Marvel *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 2741; Mukherji and Bhattacharyya, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, 17, 1208).

The hydrogenation of the keto-ester (IV: R = CO₂Me) was carried out with palladium on charcoal and the carbonyl group of the hydrogenated product was then reduced by the method of Huang-Minion (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2487, 1949, 71, 3301) to yield two different acidic materials: (a) liquid and (b) solid, m.p. 192-93° in in the ratio of 9:1. In order to establish the stereochemical configurations, the two acids were separately esterified and the esters were subjected to the Grignard reaction with phenylmagnesium bromide. The carbinol obtained from the liquid acid was oxidised directly or dehydrated and then oxidised according to the method of Zeiss (*ibid.*, 1948, 70, 858) to furnish *trans-syn-cis*-9-ketoperhy-

drophenanthrene (VIII). (Linstead *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 1428; *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 64, 1991 and subsequent papers; Marvel and White, *ibid.*, 1940, 62, 2739). The carbinol from the crystalline acid was dehydrated to the unsaturated compound which was then ozonised to provide *trans-anti-trans* ketone (IX) (Bhattacharyya, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 85; Linstead *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

*EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl 2-Carboethoxycyclohexyl-1-cyanoacetate (II: $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{CN}$).—To a suspension of 10% Pd—C (0.8 g.) in 95% ethanol (40 c.c.) was added a solution of ethyl 2-carboethoxycyclohexylidene-1-cyanoacetate (I, 53 g.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. After an induction period of 35 minutes the average rate of absorption of hydrogen was 160 c.c. per hour and the total absorption was 4870 c.c. of hydrogen at $\pm 8^\circ$. The mixture was filtered and ethanol was distilled under reduced pressure. Distillation of the residual liquid afforded a colorless mobile oil, b.p. $135.40^\circ/0.7$ mm, yield 52 g. (Found: C, 62.64; H, 7.80. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 62.92; H, 7.86%).

γ -Cyano- γ -carboethoxy- γ -(2-carboethoxycyclohexyl)-butyronitrile (II: $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CN}$; $R_3 = \text{CN}$).—A mixture of the above cyano-ester (13.4 g.), freshly distilled acrylonitrile (3.18 g.) and peroxide-free dioxane (5 g.) was cooled for 30 minutes at 0° – 10° . To it was added "Triton B" (0.4 c.c.) dropwise with constant swirling. Immediately the colour of the solution turned brown. The reaction was allowed to proceed at 0° – 10° for one hour and then at room temperature for 48 hours. The reaction mixture was taken up in benzene, washed thoroughly with 2N-HCl solution and finally with water. After removal of the solvent the liquid was distilled, b.p. $185.90^\circ/0.7$ mm; n_D^{20} 1.4842; yield 15.0 g. (Found: C, 63.71; H, 7.62. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 63.75; H, 7.5%).

Methyl γ -Carbomethoxy- γ -(2-carbomethoxycyclohexyl)-butyrate (II: $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{Me}$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$; $R_3 = \text{H}$).—A mixture of the above dicarboxy-ester (34 g.) and HCl (conc., 300 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 50 hours. After 30 hours' refluxing the reaction mixture was homogeneous. The acidic mixture was concentrated in a steam-bath when white crystals of the tricarboxylic acid (II: $R = R_1 = \text{CO}_2\text{H}$; $R_2 = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{H}$), m.p. 165° , separated out. A portion of the crystalline material

* All m.p.s. are uncorrected. The U.V.-spectrum was measured by the Unicam spectrophotometer (SP 500).

was recrystallised three times from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether to afford the pure material, m.p. 171° . (Found: C, 55.65; H, 7.29; N.E., 85.0. $C_{13}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 55.81; H, 6.97%; N.E., 86). The crude acid containing ammonium chloride, obtained by evaporation, was dried and esterified by refluxing with methanolic (73 c.c.) sulphuric acid (10 c.c., d 1.84) for 50 hours. The cooled reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice and the precipitated oil was extracted four times with ether-benzene mixture. The solvent layer was washed successively with water, 2% ice-cold sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was distilled, b.p. $174-76^{\circ}/2$ mm; $n_D^{21.5}$ 1.465; yield 22.7 g. (Found: C, 60.21; H, 8.30. $C_{15}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 60.00; H, 8.0%).

Dimethyl trans-1-Decalone-2:4-dicarboxylate (III: R=H; $R_1=R_2=CO_2Me$).—To a suspension of sodium dust (2.3 g.) in dry benzene (75 c.c.) was added a solution of the above triester (15 g.) in dry benzene (25 c.c.) containing dry methanol (0.5 c.c.). The mixture was then refluxed for 5 hours under nitrogen atmosphere. The sodio enolate of the β -keto-diester was insoluble in benzene. The reaction mixture was cooled and acidified with cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted thrice with ether-benzene mixture. The combined solvent was washed successively with water, ice-cold 2% sodium hydroxide solution and finally with water. The solvent was removed. Distillation of the residual liquid gave a colorless, thick, mobile oil, b.p. $155-60^{\circ}/1.5$ mm; $n_D^{21.5}$ 1.4958; yield 9.2 g. The alcoholic solution of the liquid showed a strong violet coloration with ferric chloride solution. (Found: C, 63.01; H, 7.80. $C_{14}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 62.68; H, 7.46%).

trans-1-Decalone-4-carboxylic Acid (III: R= R_1 =H; $R_2=CO_2H$).—A mixture of the above β -keto-diester (1.2 g.) and HCl (conc., 12 c.c.) was heated under reflux for 16 hours. The acidic mixture was diluted with water and after saturation with ammonium chloride it was repeatedly extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was then washed once with cold saturated brine solution, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent was removed. The liquid residue (0.8 g.) on evaporative distillation at $130-40^{\circ}/0.2$ mm yielded a yellow semi-solid mass which was then kept under petroleum ether and scratched with a glass rod, when a solid, m.p. 141° , was obtained. This on four crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded the pure white material, m.p. $156.5-157^{\circ}$ [lit. m.p. $153.2-54.7^{\circ}$]. (Found: C, 67.51; H, 8.42. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$: C, 67.34; H, 8.16%).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared by the sodium acetate method, was crystallised three times from dilute methanol to furnish the pure material, m.p. $215-16^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 56.52; H, 7.84. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3N_2$ requires C, 56.91; H, 7.51%).

The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* was prepared directly from the semicarbazone (0.1 g.) and 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (0.1 g.) in 95% ethanol (10 c.c.) by refluxing with 6 drops of HCl (conc.). Two recrystallisations from a mixture of alcohol and ethyl acetate furnished orange needles, m.p. 215° (decomp.) [lit. m.p. $210.5-213^{\circ}$ (decomp.), and m.p. 200° (decomp.)].

Dimethyl 2-Methyl-trans-1-decalone-2:4-dicarboxylate (III: R = Me; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me).—(a). To a cold suspension of sodium dust (0.9 g.) in dry benzene (40 c.c.) was added a solution of the β -keto-diester (8.7 g.) in dry benzene (15 c.c.) dropwise with swirling in an atmosphere of nitrogen, and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 20 hours at room temperature. To the white precipitate of the sodio enolate was added methyl iodide (6 c.c.) and the reaction mixture was refluxed for 5 hours. It was cooled, diluted with water and the aqueous layer was extracted twice with benzene. After removal of the solvent, the residual oil was distilled, b.p. 160°/1.5 mm; n_D^{25} 1.483; yield 6.3 g. The liquid gave no positive ferric chloride coloration in alcoholic solution. (Found: C, 63.58; H, 8.0. C₁₅H₂₂O₄ requires C, 63.86; H, 7.80%).

(b). To the sodio enolate, prepared from trimethyl ester (11.5 g.), sodium dust (1.9 g.), dry benzene (75 c.c.) and methanol (0.5 c.c.), as described before, was added methyl iodide (10 c.c.), and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hours, cooled, worked up as above and distilled; yield 7.3 g.

2-Methyl-trans-1-decalone-4-carboxylic Acid (III: R = Me; R₁=H; R₂=CO₂H).—A mixture of the above methylated keto-diester (2.7 g.) and HCl (conc., 30 c.c.) was refluxed for 16 hours. On cooling, a solid acid (1.7 g.), m.p. 166°, separated out from the solution, and a further quantity (0.3 g.) of the acid was obtained by repeated extraction of the aqueous acidic layer with ether. The crude acid after four crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded the pure material, m.p. 183-84°. (Found: C, 68.38; H, 8.42. C₁₂H₁₈O₃ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57%). This keto-acid did not furnish any semicarbazone by the usual methods.

2- γ -Ketobutyl-2:4-dicarbomethoxy-trans-1-decalone (III: R = CH₂CH₂COMe; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me).—To cold sodium methoxide, prepared from sodium (0.46 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.) and absolute methanol (10 c.c.) by refluxing, was added dropwise a solution of the β -keto-diester (III: R=H; R₁=R₂=CO₂Me; 5.3 g.) in dry benzene (20 c.c.) with constant swirling under nitrogen atmosphere and the reaction was allowed to proceed for 20 hours at room temperature. To the insoluble sodio enolate of the β -keto-diester, cooled in an ice-bath for 1 hour, was added slowly a solution of the methiodide, prepared from redistilled 1-diethylaminobutanone-3 (5 g.) in absolute methanol (20 c.c.), with constant swirling. All the sodio enolate dissolved after 30 minutes' swirling. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature for 24 hours to complete the reaction. The clear straw-yellow solution was diluted with water and extracted thrice with benzene. The solvent layer was washed with HCl (dil.) and finally with water. After removal of the solvent, the residual liquid was fractionated: (1) b.p. 150-60°/1.2 mm; 0.85 g. and (2) b.p. 200-205°/1.2 mm; n_D^{25} 1.4960; 4.35 g. The viscous sticky mass could not be crystallised. (Found: C, 64.15; H, 7.87. C₁₈H₂₆O₆ requires C, 63.90; H, 7.70%).

9-Carbomethoxy-1:2:3:4b:5:6:7:8:8a:9:10:10a-dodecahydrophenanthrene-3-one (IV: R=CO₂Me).—A solution of the above condensation product (2 g.) in a mixture of HCl (conc., 20 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (60 c.c.) was refluxed for 14 hours under nitrogen. Heating for a longer period decreased the yield. After removal of most of the

acetic acid and HCl under reduced pressure, the residue was diluted with ice-water and the aqueous layer was extracted several times with ether. The solvent layer was washed once with brine solution and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, a semi-solid mass was obtained; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 236 m μ (log ϵ 3.8). The crude acid was then esterified with diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (1 g.), in ethereal solution. After the evolution of nitrogen had ceased, the excess of diazomethane was destroyed by the addition of acetic acid. The ester was worked up as described before and then evaporatively distilled at 140-45°/0.8-1.0 mm; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 236 m μ (log ϵ 3.91); yield 1.0 g. (Found: C, 72.91; H, 8.81. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 73.28; H, 8.39%).

The *semicarbazone* of the unsaturated keto-ester was prepared in the usual way and was crystallised from dilute methanol in pure white crystals, m.p. 215° (decomp.); $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{alc}}$ 266 m μ (log ϵ 4.47). This semicarbazone was very light-sensitive and turned yellow on keeping in light. (Found: C, 64.31; H, 7.52; N, 13.41. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{23}\text{O}_2\text{N}_3$ requires C, 63.95; H, 7.83; N, 13.18%).

9-Methylphenanthrene (V).—To a solution of lithium aluminium hydride (0.6 g.) in pure dry ether (20 c.c.), prepared by refluxing on the water-bath for 1 hour, was added dropwise a solution of the keto-ester (IV: R=CO₂Me; 1.26 g.) in dry ether (15 c.c.) with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 hours to complete the reaction. The excess of the hydride was decomposed by adding water dropwise and then ice-cold 10% H₂SO₄ solution (50 c.c.) was added to it. The acidic layer was extracted four times with ether. The combined ether extract was successively washed with water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution, finally with water and then dried. After removal of the solvent, a yellow, sticky, semi-solid mass (1 g.) was obtained. An intimate mixture of the above diol (0.45 g.) and powdered selenium (2 g.) was heated at 320-40° for 24 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and the dehydrogenated product was thoroughly extracted with hot benzene. The combined benzene extract was distilled. To the residue, thus obtained, was added 95% ethanol (20 c.c.), boiled and filtered. To the hot concentrated filtrate was added a saturated alcoholic solution of picric acid (0.3 g.). The mixture was cooled when orange, needle-shaped picrate (0.2 g.), m.p. 148°, was obtained. Two crystallisations from ethanol afforded orange needles, m.p. 151° [lit. m.p. 151-53° for the picrate]. (Found: N, 10.14. Calc. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_7\text{N}_3$: N, 9.98%).

The *picrate* (0.1 g.), m.p. 148°, was decomposed by passing the benzene solution through alumina (Merck & Co., 10 g.). The alumina column was eluted with the same solvent and the combined benzene solution was distilled. The residue was dissolved in 95% ethanol (5 c.c.) and allowed to stand for 18 hours when white crystals of 9-methylphenanthrene, m.p. 87°, separated out; yield 0.07 g. The hydrocarbon was then evaporatively distilled at 100-105°/0.15-0.2 mm and the sublimate on three crystallisations from 95% ethanol afforded the pure material, m. p. 91° [lit. m. p. 90-91°]. Mixed m. p. with an authentic sample did not show any depression.

trans-syn-cis & *trans,anti-trans-9-Carboxyperhydrophenanthrene* (VI & VII: R = CO₂H).—To a suspension of 10% Pd—C (0.5 g.) in 95% ethanol (20 c.c.) was added a solution of the unsaturated keto-ester (IV: R = CO₂Me, 4.5 g.) in 95% ethanol (15 c.c.) in an atmosphere of hydrogen. When the absorption of hydrogen was slowed down after 6 hours, fresh catalyst (0.1 g.) was added to complete the hydrogenation. On working up as before, the residue was distilled, b. p. 160-65°/0.8 mm; n_D^{25} 1.4922; yield 4.1 g. (Found: C, 72.44; H, 9.38. C₁₈H₂₄O₂ requires C, 72.73; H, 9.09%).

To a solution of the above saturated keto-ester (1.0 g.) in diethyleneglycol (10 c.c.) was added 85% hydrazine hydrate (1.5 c.c.) solution and the mixture was refluxed at 140°. After 1 hour a concentrated solution of KOH (1 g. KOH in 1 c.c. of water and 5 c.c. of diethyleneglycol) was added to the reaction mixture which was again refluxed for 1 hour. Then the condenser was taken out the temperature was raised to 200° and kept there for 1½ hours more. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into iced HCl (5 c.c.), when a solid with adhering gum separated out. The aqueous acidic layer was saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted four times with ether. The combined ethereal layer was washed once with brine solution, dried and distilled. The residue, left after removal of the ether, was dissolved in a mixture of ether and petroleum ether and allowed to stand at room temperature for 20 hours, when a solid acid, m.p. 190-91°, crystallised out. Two crystallisations from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether afforded the pure acid (VII: R = CO₂H; 50 mg.), m. p. 192-93°. (Found: C, 76.33; H, 10.28. C₁₈H₂₄O₂ requires C, 76.26; H, 10.17%). From the mother-liquor was obtained a liquid acid (VI: R = CO₂H; 450 mg.) which was purified by evaporative distillation at 140-45°/0.3 mm. (Found: C, 76.36; H, 10.50. C₁₈H₂₄O₂ requires C, 76.26; H, 10.17%).

trans-syn-cis-9-Carbomethoxyperhydrophenanthrene (VI: R = CO₂Me).—To a cold ethereal solution of the saturated liquid acid (VI: R = CO₂H; 2.7 g.) was added a cold ethereal solution of diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (2.5 g.). The ester was worked up as described before and then evaporatively distilled at 105-10°/0.2 mm; yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 76.52; H, 10.50. C₁₈H₂₄O₂ requires C, 76.84; H, 10.40%).

trans-anti-trans-9-Carbomethoxyperhydrophenanthrene (VII: R = CO₂Me).—The solid acid (VI: R = CO₂H; 1.5 g.), m.p. 185°, was esterified with diazomethane, prepared from nitrosomethylurea (2 g.) in ethereal solution, adopting the same method as described before. The ester was purified by evaporative distillation at 100°/0.2 mm, yield 1.5 g. (Found: C, 76.48; H, 10.26. C₁₈H₂₄O₂ requires C, 76.84; H, 10.40%).

trans-syn-cis-9-Ketoperhydrophenanthrene (VIII).—To the Grignard complex, prepared from magnesium (1.0 g.) and bromobenzene (5 c.c.) in dry ether (30 c.c.), was added a solution of the ester (VI: R = CO₂Me; 2 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (15 c.c.) and the reaction was allowed to proceed at room temperature for 16 hours and then refluxed for 4 hours on a water-bath. It was cooled and the Grignard complex was decomposed with an excess of 25% aqueous solution of ammonium chloride and was extracted thoroughly with an ether-benzene mixture. The solvent layer was successively washed with water, saturated sodium bicarbonate solution and finally with

water. After removal of the solvent, the crude product was refluxed for 2 hours with a 10% aqueous NaOH solution. It was cooled, diluted with water and extracted thrice with ether-benzene mixture. The solvent layer was washed with water and the residue after removal of the solvents was evaporatively distilled at 140-45°/0.2 mm, yield 1.7 g. (Found: C, 86.89; H, 9.40. $C_{27}H_{34}O$ requires C, 86.63; H, 9.09%). An intimate mixture of the carbinol (0.5 g.) and fused potassium hydrogen sulphate (1.5 g.), taken in a sublimation tube, was introduced in an air-chamber, previously heated to 180° and kept at that temperature for 20 minutes under nitrogen atmosphere. The dehydrated product was evaporatively distilled at 130-35°/0.2 mm; $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alio}}$ 249 m μ (log ϵ 4.0); yield 0.3 g.

A solution of chromic anhydride (3 g.) in a mixture of water (3 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (G. R. quality, 21 c.c.) was added dropwise in 20 minutes to a solution of the above carbinol (1.47 g.) in glacial acetic acid (12 c.c.) at 80° and the reaction was allowed to proceed at 75-80° for 4 hours. The clear green solution was cooled, diluted with water and the product was extracted with ether. The ether extract was successively washed with water, 5% aq. NaOH solution and finally with water. After removal of the solvent, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 95°/2 mm; yield 0.3 g. The liquid ketone was then converted into the orange-red 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 230-32°, which on purification through chromatography and recrystallisation from a mixture of benzene and ethanol furnished the pure material, m.p. 236-37°, yield 0.3 g. (lit. m.p. 236-37° and 232-33°), (Found: N, 14.80. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{20}O_4N_4$: N, 14.50%). The unsaturated diphenylene compound was also oxidised with chromic anhydride in glacial acetic acid to furnish the same ketone.

Cleavage of the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was carried out according to the procedure of Djerassi (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1003). A mixture of the above 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (0.3 g.), pure chloroform (15 c.c.), pyruvic acid (N. E. 102; 21 c.c.) and approximately 4N anhydrous hydrobromic acid in acetic acid (2 c.c.) was kept at 50-60° for 4 hours with constant stirring, when the liquid assumed a light yellow colour. The reaction mixture was homogeneous during the reaction period. After dilution with chloroform and extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution, the organic layer was dried and distilled. The residue, containing a few crystals of 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, was dissolved in excess of dry petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chromatographed on alumina (30 g.). The chromatogram was eluted with the same solvent (200 c.c.). The solvent was distilled off and the residue dried under suction. On cooling, the liquid solidified completely, m.p. 53°. The ketone on evaporative distillation at 90-95°/2 mm furnished the pure material, m.p. 56-57°, yield 0.1 g. (lit. m.p. 56.5-57°). (Found: C, 81.47; H, 10.95. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{22}O$: C, 81.55; H, 10.70%).

trans-anti-trans-9-Ketoperhydrophenanthrene (IX).—To the Grignard complex, prepared from magnesium (0.75 g.) and bromobenzene (4 c.c.) in pure dry ether (30 c.c.), was added a solution of the ester (VII: R = CO₂Me; 1.5 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (15 c.c.) and the reaction was carried out as described before. The carbinol (1.5 g.) was evaporatively distilled at 140-45°/0.2 mm. It was dehydrated with fused potassium

hydrogen sulphate (3 g.) using the same procedure as described before to yield the unsaturated compound (1.1 g.), evaporatively distilling at $130^{\circ}/0.2$ mm; $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{ulc}}$ 249 m μ (log ϵ 3.93). The latter compound (1.1 g.) was then ozonised in cold chloroform solution (30 c.c.). The ketone, thus obtained, was converted into the 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (0.5 g.), m.p. $198-205^{\circ}$, purified through chromatography over alumina, and then cleaved, adopting the same procedure as before. But, instead of a solid ketone, a liquid ketone (0.2 g.) was obtained. The ketone was, however, further purified through its oxime as follows.

A mixture of the liquid ketone (50 mg.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (100 mg.), pyridine (0.1 c.c.) and methanol (2 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours. After diluting the reaction mixture the oxime, m.p. $205-207^{\circ}$, on four crystallisations from a large amount of ethanol furnished silky needles, m.p. 226° [lit. m.p. $226-27^{\circ}$, $227-28^{\circ}$, $230-33^{\circ}$]. (Found : N, 6.46. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}ON$: N, 6.33%).

The above oxime (0.1 g.) was refluxed with 5% H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) for 6 hours. The acidic solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and water, dried and distilled. The residue on evaporative distillation at $90^{\circ}/2$ mm furnished a solid ketone, m.p. 46° with an adhering oil. Two crystallisations from light petroleum ether yielded white needles, m.p. 49° [lit. m.p. $46-47^{\circ}$, 48° , 49°]. The mixed m.p. with an authentic sample of *trans-anti-trans*-9-ketoperhydrophenanthrene did not show any depression.

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DIVISION OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
JADAVPUR UNIVERSITY,
CALCUTTA-32.

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